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Mapping bioeconomy-relevant research in Amazon institutions¹

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Introduction

For Brazil to fulfil its nationally determined contributions under the Paris Accords, a new bioeconomy based on valuing the standing forest must be established for the Amazon biome (Gatti et al., 2021). This requires the development of production chains that can add value to sustainably produced non-timber forestry products to all links of the chain, especially those at the very beginning. This will allow the development of an inclusive economy that brings prosperity to the region while guaranteeing environmental protection and regeneration. For this to become a reality, the role of local scientific development is vital to benefit from local knowledge. Despite this, institutions in the Brazilian Amazon biome at present produce around 2% of Brazil's total articles, and just 3% of its PhDs.

Sustainable bioeconomy activities are knowledge intensive, requiring a conjunction of scientific research, public and private sector development, local knowledge and experience. For a chain to be both economically productive and protective of the forest, it must also offer solid public healthcare (Castro, 2022), educational opportunities and training for communities as well as social welfare. These are all associated with greater levels of economic growth and lower rates of deforestation, so are also considered.

The universities inside the Amazon biome hold a vital position, for their ability to act as an interface between scientific research and local knowledge. Their proximity to the forest should mean that they explore a different range of topics closely aligned with local priorities and small producers than institutions outside the biome. Rafols et al. (2019) found similar results comparing research priorities in research on rice.

Identifying and categorising research that is relevant for bioeconomy chains is an important, but challenging task. The range of knowledge does not apply to any single area of knowledge – it can range from physics, chemistry or medicine to public administration and tourism. The research uses a heterogeneous nomenclature to describe itself – little research that can

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contribute to bioeconomy uses “bioeconomy” as a keyword itself. It is also often published in less prominent and local sources.

Because such a study has not been undertaken for the Amazon region, this first paper aims to compare the bioeconomy relevant research output of institutions in the Amazon biome with Brazil as a whole. It will then produce a framework that will allow us to assess the importance of collaboration between local institutions and national research-intensive universities, and whether this type of collaboration has a positive effect on the applicability of research portfolios that each presents (Vonortas, 2019).

A jointly funded project between FAPESP and FAPEAM analyses the production chains of four non timber forestry products and their potential to create sustainable livelihoods in the Amazon biome; açai berries, Brazil nuts, wild cocoa and fishery of the pirarucu, tambaqui and matrinxã.

Methodology

Dimensions database was used for this study, preferred for its much larger spectrum of publication compared to Scopus or Web of Science, and greater representation of regional sources, including SciELO, as well as conference proceedings, and pre-print archives. Because many of the institutions in the Amazon prefer to publish in less mainstream resources, this was selected as the best option for this study.

An initial protocol was designed using the keywords:

amazon* AND economy OR bioeconomy OR sustainable development OR development OR innovation

It was then manually refined by removing keywords that produced erroneous results:

NOT dam NOT neurosurgery NOT alcohol NOT indoor NOT electrocardiography NOT chagas NOT covid NOT ux NOT snake NOT alzheimer*

And research, condition and disease categories that produced erroneous results:

NOT (Infectious Diseases OR Cancer OR Rare Diseases)

And fields of research:

NOT (21 History and Archaeology OR 22 Philosophy and Religious Studies OR 1103 Clinical Sciences OR 0803 Computer Software OR 0206 Quantum Physics OR 0103 Numerical and Computational Mathematics OR 0307 Theoretical and Computational Chemistry OR 0802 Computation Theory and Mathematics OR 19 Studies in Creative Arts and Writing OR 13 Education)

Results

In the past five years, 28.7% of all research on Amazon bioeconomy published by a Brazilian research organisation had the participation of an institution situated in the Amazon. This is an increase from 22.4% in the period 2007-2011, and 24% in 2012-2016. This is a gradual, and constant change.

Although this seems modest in relative terms, it should be noted that the overall absolute expansion has been huge. The overall dataset grew by 78% between the first five-year period and the second, and 53% in the second. This growth rate is far above the global average for increasing publication.

Table 1: Articles in Brazilian bioeconomy 2007-2021

Period	Published by Amazonian institution	Number of articles	% of previous period	% of total for period
2017-2021	Yes	10577	179,91	28,73
2017-2021	No	26243	144,61	71,27
2017-2021	Total	36820	153,25	
2012-2016	Yes	5879	194,22	24,47
2012-2016	No	18147	173,71	75,53
2012-2016	Total	24026	178,31	
2007-2011	Yes	3027		22,47
2007-2011	No	10447		77,53
2007-2011	Total	13474		

Table 2: Fields of research in Brazilian bioeconomy 2007-2021

Name	Publications
Biological Sciences	10125
Ecology	4707
Environmental Sciences	4570
Environmental Science and Management	3346
Earth Sciences	2965
Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences	2830
Engineering	2609
Medical and Health Sciences	2541
Genetics	2285
Studies in Human Society	2000
Plant Biology	1918
Public Health and Health Services	1426
Information and Computing Sciences	1394
Forestry Sciences	1261
Geology	1248
Evolutionary Biology	1077
Soil Sciences	1014
Chemical Sciences	1006
Zoology	875

The publication output in Amazon institutions more than trebled between the periods 2007-2012 and 2017-2021: from 3,027 to 10,577. This is a huge increase that is far greater than the general growth observed for all areas of knowledge in these institutions.

Table 3: Bioeconomy related open datasets produced in Brazil 2007-2021

Period	Published by Amazonian institution	Datasets	% of previous period	% of total for current period
2017-2021	Yes	813	309,13	57,01
2017-2021	No	613	408,67	42,99
2017-2021	Total	1426		
2012-2016	Yes	263	1.547,06	63,68
2012-2016	No	150	2.142,86	36,32
2012-2016	Total	413		
2007-2011	Yes	17		
2007-2011	No	7		
2007-2011	Total	24		

Table 4: Number of grants awarded to Brazilian institutions on bioeconomy 2007-2021

Period	Published by Amazonian institution	Number of grants awarded	% of previous period	% of total for current period
2017-2021	Yes	267	85,58	36.2
2017-2021	No	469	87,83	63.8
2017-2021	Total	736	87,00	
2012-2016	Yes	312	1.485,71	36.8
2012-2016	No	534	193,48	63.2
2012-2016	Total	846	284,85	
2007-2011	Yes	21		7.0
2007-2011	No	276		93.0
2007-2011	Total	297		

Table 5: Bioeconomy patents produced in Brazil 2007-2021

Period	Published by Amazonian institution	Number of patents granted	% of previous period	% of total for current period
2017-2021	Yes	55	220,00	8,76
2017-2021	No	573	151,59	91,24
2017-2021	Total	628	155,83	
2012-2016	Yes	25	416,67	6,20
2012-2016	No	378	192,86	93,80
2012-2016	Total	403	199,50	
2007-2011	Yes	6		
2007-2011	No	196		
2007-2011	Total	202		

Discussion

From this initial survey, we can conclude that the increase in bioeconomy relevant publications have increased at a huge rate over the past fifteen years, far faster than the overall rate of scientific growth in the period. Institutions in the Amazon biome produce a small, but significant body of work, and one that is growing as a proportion of the total output at a steady rate of around 3-4% every five years.

Amazon institutions produce a large proportion of the open datasets compared to Brazilian institutions as a whole – this suggests that they are much more engaged in primary research and data collection than other institutions. This offering of open datasets forms an important resource for other scientists outside of the biome lacking access to the forest itself, and the populations living within it.

Relatively speaking, if Amazonian institutions carry out a large duty of collecting primary information, they do not produce as many patents as institutions in other regions. This means that many of the relevant technological solutions are being produced outside of the region.

Conclusion

The dataset of bioeconomy related research being produced in the Amazon biome is of potential value for university leaders, funding agencies and civil society engaged with the construction of sustainable production chains in the Amazon region. In this initial study, we have demonstrated that this research is growing at a rapid rate, and these institutions make a large contribution to the collection of primary sources in the biome, serving as an important source for global research into the forest.

Next Steps

The next steps in this research will be to begin to map the contents inside this dataset, to determine exactly what kinds of research occur at each type of institution. The next stage will look at the research related to four specific bioeconomy chains: açai berries, Brazil nuts, wild cocoa and fishery of pirarucu, tambaqui and matrinxã. This stage will analyse links in the chain where the research is strongest and identify knowledge deficits and underserved needs. Such an

understanding of how research applies to different chains will allow us to develop novel indicators related to how well research fulfils declared needs.

The final stage will be to study the usage of scientific knowledge by different actors in the chain, identifying blockages, successful communication strategies and areas where scientific communication with society can be strengthened in the Amazon region.

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